

*Innovative Large-Scale
Production of Affordable Clean
Burning Solid Biofuel and
Water in Southern Africa*

INNOVATIVE FINANCING TOOLBOX FOR BIOMASS MSMES

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SteamBioAfrica

Innovative Large-Scale Production of Affordable Clean Burning Solid Biofuel and Water in Southern Africa: transforming bush encroachment from a problem into a secure and sustainable energy source

Deliverables: D10.5 Innovative Financing Toolbox for Biomass MSMEs

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
MSMEs	Micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises
NGOs	Non-governmental organisations
SBA	SteamBioAfrica
SHS	Superheated steam

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report looks into the issue of access to finance by micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) in the biomass sector of Botswana, Namibia and South Africa as part of the EU Horizon 2020 SteamBioAfrica project's objective to facilitate the commercialisation of the new clean-burning solid biofuel generated by the superheated steam (SHS) technology that the project is promoting.

This report identifies **four types of financing sources** relevant to the biomass sector, i.e., traditional financing, digital financing, innovative financing, and informal financing. Each type has a prospect of providing access to MSME finance particularly to those operating in the biomass value chains in the three countries. Some other findings include:

- MSME financing schemes are mostly offered by **government-initiated funds** and **commercial banks**, particularly development banks. These organisations play a big role in the financing of biomass MSMEs. This is partly due to the fact that the SBA solid biofuel is new to the market and it is a simple product used for cooking and heating of homes.
- **Public finance** needs to be raised but will also be limited in the face of the scale of MSME investments required. **Innovative green finance** platforms, policies and instruments in the **blended finance** arena are necessary but will not be sufficient; they need to be coupled with national policies establishing enabling conditions for **private investment** as well as **MSME capacity building** on financial literacy and business planning.
- **Innovative and digital financing** can play a bigger role in enhancing MSME access to finance as the technology is spreading in the region. **Facilitating partnerships** between commercial banks and agtechs holds potential to reduce costs and capitalise on agtechs' ability to reach and de-risk rural consumers.
- Potential contribution of **digital financial services** to improve efficiencies (thereby reducing cost) and making access to such services far more widespread (thereby increasing reach) requires on-going support from all stakeholders, including regulatory authorities.
- The use of alternative data to develop new credit products (which can de-risk MSMEs) and the potential of digital financial services is key in providing banking services to MSMEs and **digitising specific value chains**, such as the new solid biofuel, in the process.
- Key players in innovative and digital financing still favour digital and fintech startups more than small agri-forestry enterprises. **Biomass MSMEs with clear business plans** and **innovative business models** can still benefit from other alternative financing such as **crowdfunding**, or a combination of other financing schemes (government-initiated funds, MSME loans by commercial banks, and microfinance).
- **Consistent historical track record** with banks and financial institutions is particularly important for MSMEs. MSMEs that have worked with the SBA project may not need a huge credit from banks, that necessitate a sizable collateral. A fintech company, e.g. Nomanini¹ in South Africa, showcases how fintech can strategically bridge MSMEs in

¹ Nomanini (online). Unlock the potential of Africa's informal markets.

<https://nomanini.com/solutions/#:~:text=The%20end%2Dto%2Dend%20fintech,banking%20services%20to%20their%20communities>.

the retail sector with the financing they need by helping MSMEs build historical track records.

- **Women-owned enterprises** often face a disproportionate challenge in accessing finance as banks consider women as 'riskier clientele'. **Through a participatory approach**, governments can formulate differentiated financial inclusion policies for women-owned MSMEs. Such policies can also target financial literacy among women-owned MSMEs through targeted capacity building programmes.

CONCLUSIONS

Access to finance (A2F) has been highlighted in various reports as a major challenge facing MSMEs in the Global South. However, there was no information yet on access to finance by MSMEs operating in the biomass sector in the Southern African region, where the SteamBioAfrica project is currently working to promote the SHS technology and new clean-burning solid biofuel as sustainable solutions to the environmental challenge facing Botswana, Namibia and South Africa, which is posed by bush encroachment.

Clearly, there is a need to explore the existing financial landscape in the three countries to identify financing sources that can potentially be accessed by the biomass MSMEs, not only by those operating in the downstream value chains (distribution, retail, and consumption stages), but also by MSMEs operating in the upstream (bush harvesting, solid biofuel manufacturing).

As part of the Work Package 10 (WP10) – that seeks to facilitate a wide-scale commercialisation of the new solid biofuel – the SBA project set out to identify relevant financial sources for the biomass MSMEs. This endeavour has resulted in several key findings that have been presented in the Executive Summary. On the project level, however, it can be emphasised that **MSME capacity building on financial literacy and business planning are the first step** toward improved access to MSME finance. The MSME financing schemes that are offered by **government-initiated funds and commercial banks** require formality which, in turn, requires a certain level of financial literacy and business planning – without which it is almost impossible for biomass MSMEs to apply for a financing. This is despite the fact that governments and commercial banks have a dedicated MSME financing scheme.

This study also found that the financial landscape in the three countries is currently changing to embrace **digital transformation** as the digital financial technology offers new business models and opportunities – which often can **help de-risk small entrepreneurs in rural areas**. Reports show how the governments in Botswana, Namibia and South Africa are in the process of adopting digital financial technology, particularly through providing the much-needed policies and regulatory frameworks. As digital technologies offer new scopes of financial services to businesses – which did not exist previously, it is vital for the governments to actively engage with financial technological (fintech) companies to identify new services that may cater to the needs of biomass MSMEs, as the problem of MSMEs' limited access to finance seems to remain pervasive in the biomass value chains in the Southern Africa. In

Namibia, for example NAMFISA² organised a Fintech Square Program to encourage fintech startups in the country.

This A2F challenge needs to be addressed as countries seek to realise their **sustainable development goals (SDGs) and climate goals**. It is known that 81% of the African population depend on solid biofuels for daily economic, household and cooking activities. Furthermore, among the various bioenergy sources available in Sub-Saharan Africa, solid biofuels contribute to over 60% of the total bioenergy supply. This provides a huge economic potential to the economy. At the same time, it is found out that there are 60 million MSMEs shaping African economies, producing about half of countries' GDPs and accounting for 90% of businesses while providing approximately 60% of employment. This highlights the importance of supporting the biomass MSMEs to access finance and expand their operations.

1 OVERVIEW

1.1 Africa and the biomass sector

Africa is currently experiencing a strong economic growth and showing positive trends in human development indicators (United Nations, 2024). Access to modern and long-term sustainable energy will be critical to maintain and accelerate these positive signals. Great potential of the continent is its abundant renewable resources that could spur a continued economic growth, accelerate social development and help the continent's transition to a sustainable energy system providing universal energy access.

Meanwhile, it is estimated that investing in climate mitigation actions in Africa presents a US\$3 trillion economic investment opportunity in the continent by 2030, meaning adaptation of the African private sector to a green economy is vital for its future. Furthermore, the mostly young population in Africa is expected to meet high unemployability rates in their future, indicating the need for new business models that ensure sustainable and resilient jobs (Runde et al., 2021).

Against this backdrop, Southern African countries are currently facing **challenges posed by bush encroachment**, where the overgrowths compete for water and land with farmlands and livestock. The encroachment is caused by a combination of factors, including climate change and human activities. The bush encroachment has changed the landscape and limited the wildlife movement and migration to the detriment of not only the farmlands but also the tourism sector. However, bush control proves to be uneconomical for landowners (farmers) since it incurs high costs (e.g., labour, equipment) that may not be possible to be recovered. Hence, it is imperative to find ways to create economic value out of the "unwanted" biomass so as to finance **a sustainable land management** in the long term.

Biomass is derived from organic material such as trees, plants, and agricultural and urban waste. It can be used for heating, electricity generation, and transport fuels. The use of biomass can help diversify Southern African countries' energy supply, facilitate growth and create jobs, as well as lower the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. In the European Union

² NAMFISA (online). Fintech square program. <https://www.namfisa.com.na/fintech/>

(EU), biomass is seen as an important source of energy needed in the electricity production to balance variable renewables (European Commission, 2021).

In Africa, biomass is used as energy directly for heating or indirectly as biofuels. The biofuels include wood chips, sawdust, firewood, manure, and wood pellets. **Woody biomass is a promising domestic energy source.** It was reported that 81% of the African population depend on solid biofuels for daily economic, household and cooking activities. The wide availability of biomass obtained from agroforestry wastes justifies its high preference by the population and businesses alike (Nyika et al., 2020)

Among the various bioenergy sources available in Africa, solid biofuels contribute to over 47% of total bioenergy supply (Figure 1). In Sub-Saharan Africa, solid biofuels play an even larger role and contribute to over 60% of the total bioenergy supply. This huge potential offers not only **climate benefits**, but also **socio-economic benefits**.

Figure 1: The potential of bioenergy in Africa (Source: Stecher et al., 2013)

1.2 *The SteamBioAfrica project*

The EU-funded Horizon 2020 SteamBioAfrica project seeks to create a commercially viable technology solution that will stimulate the harvesting of invasive woody biomass, creating net economic, social, and environmental benefits. The project is undertaken in three Southern African countries, which are Botswana, Namibia, and South Africa. The innovative superheated steam (SHS) technology demonstrated in this project is set to produce a new, affordable clean-burning solid biofuel as a substitute to burning firewood or charcoal, through **transforming the bush encroachment problem into a solution for a secure and sustainable bioenergy source.**

Reported by many researchers, the bush encroachment degrades millions of hectares across Southern Africa through stifling herbaceous plants, reducing biodiversity, depleting groundwater reserves, and degrading the soil. Its negative ecosystem impact undermines surrounding communities' food and water security (Sebitloane et al, 2020). Encroachment diminishes and weakens productive farmland and rangelands, reducing livestock productivity (Mugasi et al, 2000).

In the face of this huge environmental – but also social and economic – problems posed by bush encroachment, the SBA project demonstrates how a continuous superheated steam torrefaction of biomass, that generates a clean burning high-calorific-value (CV) solid biofuel and a condensate rich in biochemicals, could be a solution for Southern Africa.

As part of the endeavour, this Work Package 10 (WP10) promotes the uptake of the clean-burning solid biofuel as a secure and sustainable bioenergy source. The biomass for the solid biofuel is harvested using sustainable methods that promote sustainable land restoration. It is, therefore, **a better and sustainable alternative** to other solid biofuels which are produced through **unsustainable harvesting** of wood for firewood and charcoal. The unsustainable harvesting has contributed to **land degradation, deforestation and climate change**. With respect to land degradation and deforestation, charcoal is of greater concern than firewood as more biomass is required for conversion to charcoal (Njenga et al, 2023).

The SteamBioAfrica's business model will facilitate the restoration of land to productive use – particularly farming and eco-tourism, and create jobs and wealth at the local level. Throughout the project, a conducive policy environment, business environment and availability of affordable finance were identified as crucial pillars for the success level of the project. To bring one of the pillars forward, the report explores financing schemes available for MSMEs operating in the biomass sector.

1.3 *The role of MSMEs*

Micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) are the backbone of the African economy. Around 60 million MSMEs shape African economies, producing about half of countries' GDPs, accounting for 90% of businesses and providing approximately 60% of employment (Runde et al., 2021). They comprise the majority of private sector players in the region (Odote et al., 2022) and understandably play a key role in the development of biomass value chains. To achieve the goal of a green and long-term sustainable economy in Africa, incentivisation for MSMEs to operate in a sustainable way is crucial. However, a major problem that a large part of African MSMEs share is accessing finance. It is estimated that the total financing gap in Africa to be a massive US \$330 billion (Loock, 2022). In Sub-

Saharan Africa the finance gap – the percentage of formal MSMEs that cannot or can only partially access credit – is estimated at 51% (AFI, 2020). Considering that many entrepreneurs also work informally, the amount of unmet financing would even be higher.

It was also observed that a significant part of MSMEs has been described as “the missing middle” which particularly struggle to access financing (Figure 2). These MSMEs employ between 5 and 35 employees and have a mediocre annual turnover. This neither qualifies them for government grants as they are considered too well resourced, nor do they have success accessing capital from commercial banks because they do not have the required credit criteria (Cunha et al., 2020). It was seen that “big companies get money and microenterprises get money” (Loock, 2022), but the MSMEs in the middle miss out.

Figure 2: MSMEs in the missing Middle are falling between the cracks in South African market (Source: McKinsey, 2020)

1.4 Report structure

This Deliverable 10.5 report seeks to identify existing as well as innovative financing schemes that are available, which can support small businesses (MSMEs) getting involved in the renewable energy sector, particularly biomass. This report starts by outlining the renewable energy sector, followed by a description on the potential of the biomass sector in Sub-Saharan Africa. Afterwards, the role of MSMEs in the sector and their potential challenges, especially in financing, are described. Following this, Chapter 4 gives an overview of the identified traditional and innovative financing schemes available in Botswana, Namibia, and South Africa.

2 THE BIOMASS AND RENEWABLE ENERGY SECTOR

2.1 Africa's energy challenges

About 620 million people in Africa – more than 58% of the continent's 1.1 billion-strong population – **have no access to electricity** (BMZ Report, 2017) (Figure 3). Even in countries like South Africa, where over 80% of its population is reportedly have access to the grids, the reliability of electricity supply remains problematic. The country has grappled with an acute energy crisis characterized by rolling blackouts (“load shedding”), some lasting as long as 15 hours a day (IEA, 2023).

Since 2021, the numbers shown in Figure 3 have decreased, but still nearly 600 million Africans – equivalent to 43% of the continent's population – lacked access to electricity in 2021, most of them in Sub-Saharan Africa (IEA, 2022). Most of these people lived in rural areas, and despite numerous national initiatives, rural electrification remains a significant difficulty for most African nations. In the future, energy demand is expected to rise further with an 80% increase until 2040. Further, rising urbanisation rates will be a challenge for smaller municipalities. It is expected that by 2100, four fifths of Africans will be living in cities (BMZ Report, 2017). Hence, it needs to be ensured that the cities are thriving and able to sustain all of their habitants.

However, Africa's energy situation could worsen if existing policies and levels of ambition are maintained. At the current rate of progress, 595 million Africans will remain unconnected in 2030 (United Nations, 2023). Inadequate energy supply is the main cause of poor economic performance (BMZ report, 2017) and subsequently inescapable poverty.

According to reports, about 80% of household energy is used for cooking. In Sub-Saharan Africa alone, nearly 900 million people rely on traditional biomass for cooking, such as wood, crop residues and dung (Dagnachew et al., 2020). Traditional biomass is known to cause significant negative impacts for health, biodiversity and climate. However, there are opportunities for developing improved and modern biomass energy technologies, which offer substantial benefits in terms of enhanced quality of energy services and reduction in negative health and environmental impacts (Karekezi et al., 2004).

2.2 Regional and international commitments for the renewables

To increase the share of renewable energies, international and national policy reforms and cross-country collaboration are required. The Sustainable Development Goal 7 (SDG 7) seeks to improve access to affordable and clean energy. This goal is vital for the region's sustainable development as many people in sub-Saharan Africa do not have access to electricity and clean energy (Section 2.1). Furthermore, the sub-goal of SDG 7.1.2 seeks to increase people's access to clean fuels and technologies.

Globally, almost one-third of people cook their meals over an open fire or traditional stoves using charcoal, wood, kerosene, coal, agricultural waste, or even animal dung. In Sub-Saharan Africa, those numbers are higher – and growing – with **four out of five Sub-Saharan Africans currently without access to clean cooking**. Inefficient cooking methods release harmful substances into the atmosphere, worsening the climate crisis and causing 3.7 million premature deaths every year due to smoke inhalation and indoor air pollution.

Women and children are disproportionately represented in those figures, as are people from Sub-Saharan African countries (IEA, 2023).

Regional cooperation and integration initiatives are being pursued to facilitate cross-border energy trade, infrastructure development, and resource sharing. Projects such as the West African Power Pool (WAPP) and the East African Power Pool (EAPP) aim to improve regional energy connectivity, enhance energy security, and promote sustainable development.

Besides this excerpt of some existing frameworks to enhance the use of renewable energy use in Africa, South Africa, Botswana, and Namibia each has a different policy landscape with sometimes more and sometimes less stringent policies towards a green energy transition, which can be looked at in the Deliverable 10.3 report.

In the realm of international cooperation, renewable energy research projects in Africa are being supported through programmes under the **EU Green Deal**, such as the Horizon programme, to respond to climate crises (EC, 2019). Another example is the Green People’s Energy initiative, which is funded by the German government. The initiative aims at installing an additional 300 gigawatts of energy from renewable sources by 2030 (BMZ report, 2017).

Figure 3: Electricity access in Africa (Source: United Nations, 2023)
UNECA analysis from data supplied by World Bank, 2023.

2.3 The potentials of biomass

Biomass originates from organic material from forestry and agriculture (such as trees and plants), from waste and residues of biological origin as well as the biodegradable fraction of waste. It can be used as energy directly for heating and combustion or indirectly as biofuels. Biofuel examples include wood shavings, sawdust, firewood, fruit stones (avocados, olives

and nutshells), manure, and pellets. Biomass, especially from wood, is a promising domestic energy source. The wide availability of biomass obtained from agricultural and industrial processes' by-products justifies its high preference. Additionally, its direct and indirect uses to produce energy make it suitable in developing regions of Africa (Nyika et al, 2020).

Furthermore, Africa has a great technical potential of biomass as it has ample land for growth of bioenergy crops and has serious electricity supply problems especially in rural areas steered up by poverty and these factors could stimulate **the use of biomass as an alternative energy source**. Africa has high biomass potential by showing that its available land, harvested residues and bioenergy crops are higher compared to those of other parts of the world (Nyika et al, 2020).

In Sub-Saharan Africa, woody biomass is the main source of energy at domestic level and **81% of the population use it** for economic and domestic activities. This rate is by far higher compared to higher income developing countries such as India and China. Although some research estimated that wood biomass use for energy would reduce globally by 2035, it is estimated that in Africa, this form of energy will contribute to 51–57% of energy consumption (Nyika et al, 2020).

All this implies the importance of biomass for local socio-economic development as **biomass offers new business opportunities and jobs, particularly in rural areas**. In this context, the SBA project creates value, i.e. a **new clean-burning solid biofuel**, out of the encroaching bush using the SHS technology. The new biofuel produces less smoke when being used for cooking and heating, contributing to users' health benefits.

3 MICRO-, SMALL- AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISE FINANCING

3.1 MSMEs and their roles in the global economy

In all regions of the world, micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) make up almost 90% of businesses (Runde et al., 2017) in both leading and developing economies (Muriithi, 2017). Hence, they are vital for local employment opportunities, tax provision and contribution to the country's gross domestic product (GDP). Besides securing economies and the salaries of many people, MSMEs are vital for future and current climate change adaptation and mitigation (Odote et al., 2022).

Although there is no commonly accepted definition, MSMEs can range from very small micro-firms with 1–5 employees and very slow growth to fast growing medium businesses earning millions of dollars and employing as many as 250 employees (Fjose et al., 2010). Current trends show that more than 50% of MSMEs in low and lower middle-income countries have fewer than 100 employees (Muriithi, 2017).

A common problem that MSMEs face around the world is their challenge in accessing finance which is key for the enterprises to survive and expand. Traditional finance institutions perceive MSMEs as financial risks due to their limited collateral and lack of financial records. Furthermore, especially micro and small enterprises lack financial literacy, adequate infrastructure and technology and are often burdened with cumbersome regulatory requirements. Globally, **20% of small businesses fail within their first year**. The failure

rate increases to 30% by the end of the second year, 50% by the fifth year, and 70% by the tenth year (System, 2023). The COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated these trends and led to an unprecedented failure rate in 2020. Table 1 showcases the specific challenges MSMEs face in the start-up, survival, growth, and sustenance stage.

Phase	Challenges
Start-up Stage	Major challenges in accessing finance reported by enterprises in this stage included the difficulty in providing collateral or a guarantee, processing time for loan applications, lack of knowledge about available schemes, and procedural complications, in that order. Enterprises also felt that high service fees for loan requests and difficulty in completing required documentation were challenges. Enterprises in the start-up stage may not be able to provide collateral for a loan and they lack knowledge about available schemes, which may hinder them from choosing the most effective option for financial assistance.
Survival Stage	The major challenges encountered by enterprises at this stage were similar to those reported by enterprises in the start-up stage, though the order was different. The difficulty in providing collateral or a guarantee and procedural complications were jointly rated the highest. The four issues of lengthy processing time, lack of knowledge about available schemes, high service fees for processing loan requests, and difficulty in completing the required documentation were rated to be equally challenging. Enterprises in this stage would usually be looking to break even with regard to investments made at start-up, and would also like to grow in their markets. They would therefore need working capital to meet their day-to-day needs. These enterprises cannot be expected to provide collateral, and would be hindered by complicated procedures and delays in loan disbursements. They also continue to lack knowledge of available financial assistance schemes.
Growth stage	Major challenges reported by enterprises in this stage included a lack of knowledge about available schemes, high service fees for processing loan requests, difficulty in provision of collateral guarantee, high rates of interest, and difficulty in completing the required documentation. As there would be both working capital and short-term loan requirements for enterprises in this stage, a lack of knowledge regarding specific schemes could hinder owners from making the most appropriate choice of financing for their enterprise. Though enterprise owners may be more inclined to seek formal financial assistance, high service fees and high rates of interest could be a deterrent. Enterprises in the growth stage also would be in a state of rapid transition and therefore the need to provide documentation for securing financial assistance would be a deterrent to accessing funds.
Sustenance Stage	Common challenges to accessing finance reported by enterprises in this stage included difficulty in provision of collateral or a guarantee, procedural complications, lack of knowledge about available schemes, lengthy processing time for loan applications, high service fees for processing loan requests, and difficulty in completing required documentation. A reasonable number of enterprises also reported high rates of interest to be a challenge. Although entrepreneurs in this stage reported procedural difficulties, processing time, and high rates of interest to be challenges accessing finance, the role of a lack of knowledge about available schemes and its influence on other challenges needs to be examined. The entrepreneurs were concerned about the requirement to have collateral or security. This would suggest that banks or lending institutions need to be more realistic about lending to MSMEs that have already established themselves in the market.

Table 1: MSMEs' challenges in accessing finance in the business stages (Source: ADB, 2016).

The MSMEs in low- and middle-income countries tend to face increased difficulties in securing a stable business due to very limited access to finance. In developing countries, credit to the private sector as a share of GDP is well below the average in high-income countries, and the lack of a well-developed financial infrastructure pose challenges for both credit providers and the enterprises using the credit (OECD, 2015). Furthermore, the International Finance Corporation (IFC) estimates that **65 million firms, or 40% of formal MSMEs in developing countries**, have an unmet financing need of \$5.2 trillion every year. Considering that many MSMEs in developing countries are operating in the informal sector, the financing gap is even larger when taking these into account (World Bank, 2019). Table 2

listed down the challenges commonly facing MSMEs in developing countries, when accessing finance.

Challenges	Start-up	Survival	Growth	Sustenance
Difficulty in collateral/guarantee	✓	✓	✓	✓
High rates of lending	✓	✓	✓	✓
Procedural complications	✓	✓	✓	✓
Lack of knowledge about available schemes	✓	✓	✓	✓
Lengthy processing time for the loan application	✓	✓	✓	✓
High service fees for processing loan requests	✓	✓	✓	✓
Difficulty in procuring/completing the required documentation	✓	✓	✓	✓
Lack of available infrastructure	✓	X	✓	✓
Lack of availability of skilled labour	✓	X	✓	✓
Absence of current account (active for 6 months)	✓	✓	✓	X
No formal accounting system	✓	✓	✓	✓
Tax compliance issues	✓	✓	✓	✓

✓ -Challenging X – Not challenging

MSMEs - Micro, Small, and Medium-Sized Enterprises

Table 2: Key challenges facing MSMEs in developing countries (Source: ADB, 2016).

According to the OECD (2022), the **MSMEs are key engines of innovation, growth, job creation** and social cohesion in high income and emerging economies as well as low-income developing countries (LIDCs). However, they experience challenges in the areas of productivity, digitalisation and others. MSMEs and entrepreneurs can only reach their full potential if they can obtain the finance they need to start, sustain and grow their business.

3.2 MSMEs in Africa

MSMEs in Africa are the backbone of the economy. According to the World Bank, African **MSMEs offer more than half of the continent's employment** and contribute to more than a third of the combined GDP of all emerging market economies. Sub-Saharan Africa alone has 44 million MSMEs (95% of all firms), almost all (97%) of which are micro enterprises (Runde et al. 2021) and together account for 50% of the total GDP (Cooper, 2023). MSMEs are particularly important due to their simple approach in response to the majority of African

people's needs by offering affordable goods and services at reasonable terms and prices, and simultaneously being a source of income and employment (Kauffmann, 2006).

Although MSMEs in Africa have one of the highest entrepreneurship rates in the world, **80% of new MSMEs fail within five years** (Adeagbo et al., 2022). Many MSMEs face numerous challenges ranging from power shortage, lack of capital, poor management skills and competencies, to inadequate information and corruption (Muriithi, 2017). Yet, **access to finance is often cited as the most difficult barrier** to be overcome, as illustrated in Figure 4.

In Sub-Saharan Africa the finance gap – the percentage of formal MSMEs that cannot or can only partially access credit – is estimated at 51%, which is the highest in the developing world (AFI, 2020). Only around one-fourth of MSMEs in sub-Saharan Africa have a bank loan or credit, and an estimated 28.3% of firms are fully credit constrained (Runde et al., 2021). This is partly due to a problem with high and unaffordable interest rates and transaction costs that the registered MSMEs encounter. Local interest rates from banks are often in the double digits, and sometimes higher than 20–25%.

Alternative finance providers, such as microfinance institutions or digital lenders (e.g., m-Shwari, Branch) may charge even higher rates, as much as 40–50%. High interest rates often deter MSMEs from trying to apply for financing (Runde et al., 2021) or lead small entrepreneurs into a situation where they are trapped in credit debts (Siyongwana, 2004).

Informal smallholders without credit history oftentimes do not have a chance to access small credit from banks. Banks often consider the cost of administering small loans to SMEs would only reduce their profits (Muriithi, 2017). To make the matter worse, poor law enforcement fails to make borrowers pay back their loans (Benzing & Chu, 2012), rendering financing to informal MSMEs very unattractive for banks.

Affordable financing had become particularly more scarce during the period of COVID-19 pandemic. It had caused a substantial economic downturn in Sub-Saharan Africa with \$115 billion in output losses and an estimated 3.3% contraction of the GDP. SMEs had been hit particularly hard with simultaneous shocks to supply and demand. They were in desperate need of liquidity at a time when financial institutions were especially hesitant to lend. If African SMEs do not receive financing support, the effects of the pandemic would be extended and exacerbated (Runde et al., 2021).

Figure 4: Share of MSMEs for which access to finance is a major obstacle, in percent
(Source: KfW, 2019)

3.3 Informal micro-enterprises

Besides access to finance, African MSMEs face another challenge. They are operating in an informal sector. This means they are not formally registered, which makes it more difficult for them to access financing.

The total MSME finance gap has a very different distribution, with a 14 percent share attributed to the microenterprise finance gap and 86 percent to the SME finance gap (Bruhn et al., 2017). Such imbalances indicate that microenterprises have relatively higher unmet needs from formal sources.

Nevertheless, the informal sector contributes an estimated 38% of Sub-Saharan Africa GDP (Ssettimba et al., 2020). The missing financial means in the sector are traditionally replaced with **informal financing** such as loans from friends and family, business partners, peer-to-peer markets and other informal financing arrangements (Bruhn et al., 2017). This poses problems due to the often very critical financial situation micro entrepreneurs' families and friends are in, as well as the risk to suffer from unserious moneylenders with astronomical interest rates (Siyongwana, 2004).

Additionally, entrepreneurs do not develop a formal credit history, which is often critical for securing financing under more favourable conditions. While MSMEs are important for

economic development, their role is rarely spelled-out with thousands of micro businesses still operating informally and not recognised as economically viable (Muriithi, 2017).

3.4 Women-owned enterprises

Women-led MSMEs account for one third the formal registered MSMEs in Africa (Ssettimba et al., 2020), hence playing a critical role for the future of the renewable energy sector. It was shown that women perform as well or better than men as entrepreneurs and agents in furthering renewable energy businesses, designing and promoting access, such as in the marketing and provision of technical support for clean cookstoves (Satyam, 2017; Shankar et al., 2015).

In data from Sub-Saharan Africa, it is shown that men provide the largest percent of workforce, while women are mostly active in the informal sector (Corfee-Morlot et al., 2019). This is largely due to gender-based discrimination and obstacles that affect their profits, community engagement, and ability to successfully maintain businesses.

Limited access to capital and limited mobility, as well as socio-cultural restrictions, often preclude a larger role for women in many modern renewable energy enterprises (IRENA, 2019). According to the World Bank, **58% of all African SMEs are women-owned**. However, these businesses continue to lag compared to men-owned businesses with fewer employees and lower than average sales (Trade and Development Bank, 2022).

With less access to land for collateral and a lack of credit histories, women are perceived as “riskier” by private lenders. Further, women oftentimes lack the necessary financial skills, risk preferences and access to networks and information. During the COVID-19 pandemic, women-owned MSMEs had faced additional strains, as women were often asked to simultaneously maintain their traditional caregiver roles and run their businesses. These disadvantages had increased their risk of closure during the pandemic (Ssettimba et al., 2020).

To support women-owned MSMEs accessing capital and finances, it is vital to eliminate credit barriers and expand financial packages that can include women. Other avenues to support women-owned MSMEs include increasing financial literacy, providing entrepreneurial training, and expanding their business networks. These goals can be accomplished through targeted technical assistance. As far as accessing capital, women can also be supported through access to property rights and eliminating the need for collateral in obtaining grants.

Women-owned businesses tend to employ more women, so supporting women-owned businesses has a greater influence on gender equity across the continent. While women-owned MSMEs create employment opportunities, they also enhance the broader economy of the African continent and can enhance larger regional and global markets (Runde et al., 2021). Table 3 describes common challenges facing women entrepreneurs. Identifying measures to tackle these challenges can enhance women’s business competitiveness and access to finance (Table 4).

Type of constraints	Key issues	Description
Financial Products and Services	Inability to meet collateral requirements	One of the major challenges, particularly to individual women customers starting or expanding their businesses or microenterprises, is their inability to meet the collateral requirements, due to inadequate laws to recognize women's property rights and the general lack of land and other property ownership by women.
	Inability to obtain loans without husband's consent	Women are often asked to obtain husbands' or male relatives' signatures in the loan application form. This may happen either due to the formal legal restrictions or informal customary practices.
	Perception of women as high risk borrowers by formal FIs	Lack of collateral, credit history and formal business registration, and lack of liquidity and available capital compel banks to charge high interest rates to women small business owners. Women's credit history and capacity of repayment in microfinance are not well registered in the credit bureaus and public offices for recognition by formal FIs.
	Constraints to scaling up loan size	Compared with micro loans offered by microfinance institutions, formal FI loans for MSMEs demand stricter loan application requirements, adopt more cumbersome application procedures, and require higher financial literacy. These requirements make it difficult not only for first-time women borrowers but also for women microfinance graduates (often individual entrepreneurs) to grow into micro and small enterprises. Women's "risk averse" nature also discourages application for larger-sized loans.
	Women's needs outside of MSME loans.	Given their time and mobility constraints, women prefer getting a range of services from the same service provider rather than accessing different services from multiple service providers. Simply providing funds will not attract women's MSMEs. Other services, such as savings, microinsurance, and pension payments, are demanded by women.
Service Outreach and Marketing	Time and mobility constraints	In many instances, women's household responsibilities limit the time women can spend on running enterprises and securing finance. Cultural constraints to women's mobility are still widespread.
	Low education and financial literacy	Women's low level of education and limited financial literacy make it difficult for them as clients to fully understand the financial products offered, documents required, and procedures to follow. This is an issue particularly when targeting low-income and rural women. Further, women entrepreneurs are likely to be risk averse in expanding their businesses and often lack self-motivation and confidence.
	Lack of gendered client and market research	Women MSME loan clients are likely to have very different needs and demands of FI services. However, FIs rarely conduct gender-differentiated client needs assessments to develop gender-specific marketing strategies.

Table 3: Common challenges facing women entrepreneurs (Source: ADB, 2014)

Financing scheme	Description
Group or third party guarantees	A number of microfinance institutions have adopted a Grameen-type group lending scheme and assignment of co-guarantors to replace the collateral requirements, although this appears more difficult with commercial banks and more innovation is needed on this front. In determining the eligibility of co-guarantors, it is important to recognize that, in some cultural contexts, it is difficult for women to request male co-guarantors or, sometimes, payment is expected if they ask local leaders to be their co-guarantor and prepare required documentation.
Secured loans	Where the regulatory framework allows, it is also a good practice to accept jewellery, machinery, farm equipment, and other movable assets available to women as collateral. In Sri Lanka, for example, gold jewellery is accepted by formal banks as security for loans.
Land loans	Where women's landownership and husband–wife joint titling is limited, FIs could provide a land loan for women to purchase land and other fixed properties that can later be used as collateral for a business loan. Uganda's DFCU Bank provides such a product.
Other physical assets as collateral	Financial institutions could extend a loan to borrowers if they can present a receipt from a certified warehouse of secured commodities or movable assets (warehouse receipts). Similarly, agribusiness and other enterprises could borrow money without collaterals and purchase machinery and vehicles based on an agreement of sale and ownership transfer to FIs once full payment is made.
Hybrid loans	Introduce a hybrid product, to combine a modified group loan (such as two women to co-guarantee for a similar business) and an individual loan to support the transition and minimise the risks of specialising into one product or business.

Table 4: Innovative financing geared toward women-owned enterprises (Source: ADB, 2014)

3.5 Financing biofuel production

The financing barrier for biofuel entrepreneurs is acute and pervasive. The total MSME financing gap is estimated to be a massive US \$330 billion (STIAS, 2022). Access to finance poses a barrier to three biofuels (briquettes, pellets, ethanol) at all levels of the value chain—not entirely surprising given the low levels of biofuel market development in Sub-Saharan Africa. SMEs and startups trying to secure non-collateralised financing at workable terms find it quite difficult.

Private-sector financing is too expensive for early-stage enterprises, and larger corporations are unwilling to invest until they see stronger proof of market and manageable operational risks. Other than local sources of finance, relatively little global impact or commercial investment capital is being directed toward the sector—under \$12 million in 2015, according to the Global Alliance for Clean Cookstoves, although investors are beginning to show rising interest (World Bank, 2017).

According to reports, the alternative biofuels are essential in reducing GHG emission generated by household cooking and heating activities, and in enhancing public health by reducing indoor pollution caused by burning of solid fuel such as firewood and charcoal. Alternative biomass fuels are a promising avenue for delivering clean cooking options to Sub-Saharan households. However, the current reach of these biofuels is still limited.

Across the region, most rural households (95%) and the majority of urban households (62%) depend on traditional solid fuels for their cooking needs. Roughly 11% use clean cooking fuels like liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) or electricity as a primary cooking fuel. Fewer than 1 million Sub-Saharan households (less than 0.5% of the region's population) use alternative

biomass fuels, such as pellets, carbonised and non-carbonized briquettes, and ethanol (World Bank, 2017).

Affordability limits the widespread adoption of alternative biomass fuels across Sub-Saharan Africa, especially for the roughly 50% of households that rely on the free collection of biomass to meet their cooking fuel needs—many are unwilling or unable to pay for clean fuels. The cost of these fuels in addition to the stoves to utilise them is unaffordable for most rural and many urban consumers. Nevertheless, a nascent market for briquettes, pellets, and ethanol is quickly growing, with many new entrants and rising interest among donors and investors (World Bank, 2017).

Still, few businesses have reached meaningful scale. Fewer than 28,000 tonnes of pellets (less than 5 thousand tons of which are for sale to households), and 80–100 thousand tons of briquettes, and 6 million litres of ethanol for cooking purposes are sold across the region per year. These numbers are low in absolute terms and in relation to distributed biofuel stoves, suggesting that most households only use biofuels as a secondary or tertiary backup.

However, **the alternative biomass cooking fuel sector is young and dynamic**, including ambitious startups poised to move beyond their pilot phase. Over the next two to three years, some could reach 50,000–100,000 customers (World Bank, 2017).

Despite many existing and new suppliers, the biofuel system's supply side experiences numerous ecosystem-level challenges, including **policy barriers** such as the poorly calibrated tax and tariff regimes that make it difficult to import fuel production equipment, biofuel stoves, and fuels, especially when local supply is inadequate, as is often the case in the early stages of market development (World Bank, 2017).

Beyond trade barriers, explicit **government endorsement** of or policies directed at encouraging a favourable enabling environment for clean alternative fuels **is often absent**. Limited awareness among consumers may be problematic for certain fuels, such as wood pellets and the SBA solid biofuel. Pellets and ethanol require properly calibrated stoves in a context of highly limited availability of technology.

The **financing barrier** for biofuel entrepreneurs is acute and pervasive, with scant global impact investment or commercial investment capital being directed at the sector. These barriers put pressure on biofuel producers and distributor margins and significantly constrain the market. Recent trends in Sub-Saharan Africa and across the world, however, are positive and reveal increasing interest from a variety of actors, including larger enterprises and policy makers (World Bank, 2017).

Despite much progress, the market is immature and questions remain regarding the viability and appropriateness of business models. Most biofuel companies in Sub-Saharan Africa have adopted a full vertical integration model to maintain control of crucial aspects of supply and distribution, but some have moved toward fuel production or last-mile distribution; and innovative business-to-business (B2B) models are emerging in the clean cooking fuel sector (World Bank, 2017).

It is common amongst MSMEs, particularly micro-enterprises, to not be aware of existing business services, financing instruments, and skills training that are available to them. This is detrimental to the financial well-being of MSMEs and the potential contribution to the economy that such enterprises can make (Ssettimba et al., 2020). The following chapter seeks to identify and collect information on innovative financing schemes that can support MSMEs, which are a key target group of the SteamBioAfrica project.

4 MSME FINANCING INSTRUMENTS IN BOTSWANA, NAMIBIA AND SOUTH AFRICA

Financial services in the form of finance schemes are critical for MSMEs to grow, from being able to carry out everyday transactions to financing expansion. To support the intended commercialisation of the SBA SHS biofuel, potential finance schemes in South Africa, Namibia, and Botswana were identified. The Information in this chapter was collected through desktop research on existing traditional as well as innovative financing schemes in the three countries, as well as through inputs from the project partners.

In the framework of Work Package 10 (WP10), the SBA project identified several financing schemes which are relevant to the MSME and biomass sector in the three countries. This activity took place between November 2023 and May 2024, and the findings are summarised in [Appendix 1](#).

In general, types of financing schemes could be identified, which are traditional finance, digital finance, innovative financing schemes, and informal finance (Table 5).

Category	Financing scheme
Traditional finance	Public finance (State-owned bank, Government-initiated funds)
	Commercial banks
	Microfinance
Digital finance	Non-bank financial institutions (NBFIs)
	Fintech
Innovative financing schemes	Blended finance
	Angel investment
	Crowdfunding
Informal finance	Social media

Table 5: Four categories of financing schemes relevant to MSMEs in the biomass sector in Southern Africa (Source: Authors)

4.1 Traditional Financing Instruments

4.1.1 Public funds

This report finds that public funds – which are offered by state-owned banks and government-initiated funds – still play a key role in MSME finance provision in Botswana, Namibia and South Africa.

The growth of alternative bioenergy in these countries therefore hinges upon government policy responses and intervention. Such policies can include a wide range of elements, including increasing the reach of credit provider market (extending credit guarantee systems, increasing public support for equity finance instruments, and supporting digital forms of access to credit), supporting the development of tools for increased efficiency of MSMEs (implementing online tools, dealing with payment delays to MSMEs), and increasing nonfinancial support (increasing financial literacy and business skills) (Ssettimba et al., 2020).

At the same time, the Alliance for Financial Inclusion (2020) reported a trend where MSMEs globally are increasingly opting for **alternative finance instruments** (e.g. asset-based instruments, online alternative finance, and venture capital), while the growth in straight debt volumes (e.g. bank lending) has been slower. Our findings show **limited MSME financing** through public financing schemes, particularly for MSMEs operating in the biomass sector in the Southern African region.

Government-initiated funds with a special focus on providing support to small businesses were identified in Botswana, Namibia and South Africa. This public financing includes local, regional, and national funds, mostly allocated through grants, loans, subsidies or other financing mechanisms. The purpose of this type of funding is often to promote local social and economic development, support public services, or stimulate sectors of the economy deemed crucial for national growth. These purposes vary largely depending on the country and local contexts. The political situation also highly influences the funding capacity of a government or the willingness to initiate new funds (e.g., upcoming elections).

The SBA project has identified nine government-initiated funds, out of which almost half offers full grants or proportional grants. The rest of public fundings offers traditional loans which have to be repaid by small businesses, albeit with special conditions.

In South Africa, the National Empowerment Fund (NEF) supports entrepreneurs from various industrial sectors with loans, including the **sustainability** and **green energy sector**. NEF offers financing options targeting startups and expansion of businesses owned by Black entrepreneurs. Yet, in NEF's Women Empowerment Fund, the minimum funding is ZAR 500,000 (EUR 25,000) to acquire capital, machinery and equipment (NEF, 2020). This indicates that the focus of the funding scheme is rather on larger projects that aim to increase and expand a business rather than on micro- and small-sized enterprises that often require smaller amounts for their daily operations. This 'problem' is mirrored in other government-initiated funds, such as funds offered by the Department of Trade, Industry and Competition (DTIC), Industrial Development Corporation (IDC), and Department of Economic Development and Environmental Affairs (DEDEA) in South Africa.

In Namibia, the Development Bank of Namibia was formed in 2002 and is mandated with financing business, including SMEs to contribute to economic growth and social development of Namibia and for the sustainable promotion of the welfare of the Namibian people. DBN financing is **linked with the key sectors** identified in the country's National Development Plan (NDP), with a particular emphasis on infrastructure development, manufacturing, tourism, telecommunications, and logistics. DBN is regarded as the biggest SME financier in the country. In 2020, DBN is reported to have provided more than N\$279.3 million to 318 SMEs, which was more than 24.5% of SME financing in the country. The SMEs receiving loans are in a wide range of industries, from business services to commercial property development to general construction to education and health care to housing and land maintenance to manufacturing and wholesale and retail commerce (IPPR, 2023). However,

no information could be found about how many agriculture / agri-forestry SMEs had accessed the financing scheme.

In our study, Development Bank of Namibia (DBN) is a showcase for **blended finance**, where the business owners' equity contribution of between 10% and 30% is required. This scheme focuses on startups and enterprises that seek to expand their businesses. Still, such businesses often are yet to acquire financial capacity in order to be able to access the blended financing schemes. It is also worth noting that due to a high rate of default cases among MSMEs, banks such as DBN tend to require co-investment by the business owners as a means for accountability.

In Botswana, there are two state-owned development finance institutions that support access to finance for small businesses and microentrepreneurs. These are the National Development Bank (NDB) and Citizens Entrepreneurial Development Agency (CEDA). The NDB is fully owned by the state and sits under the Minister of Finance and Development Planning. It provides development finance throughout the agricultural value chain and it is in the process of transitioning to become an "agri-bank". CEDA is the newest among the state-owned development finance institutions and was established in 2000. It aims to support entrepreneurship through financing projects and entrepreneurs that would not normally be funded through commercial banks. It also has a group-lending microfinance product. It is overseen by the Ministry of Entrepreneurship (World Bank, 2022).

Based on our findings, government-initiated funds seem to be the **most suitable for new and innovative MSMEs** seeking to develop a new product portfolio, such as the **SteamBioAfrica solid biofuel**, since SME financing provided by public funds often seeks to promote environmental and socio-economic development. Many of the government-initiated funds are financed by international donor organisations. The biomass MSMEs seeking to diversify their incomes through the SBA solid biofuel could consider MSME financing schemes offered by the government as the new biofuel offers positive environmental and socio-economic impacts (e.g. sustainable land restoration, creation of new source of income particularly for marginalised groups such as women and youth entrepreneurs, and new job creation).

However, many of the biomass MSMEs will need capacity building in financial and business planning. Government-initiated funds are often accessible to "more established" MSMEs as they have more capacity to meet all the formality. Besides collaterals, applicants often have to have a registered business. This requirement is something that MSMEs, especially the informal ones, often cannot meet. Also, government-initiated financing programmes tend to use lengthy and complex bureaucratic application processes. These are serious hurdles for MSMEs that generally lack the resources, time and know-how to apply for government-initiated funds.

One financing scheme that promises to facilitate the lengthy application processes is 'Chema Chema' in Botswana. The financing scheme was recently launched in April 2024 by CEDA and particularly supports **informal MSMEs** through an "easy to fill out" application form and short-term cash flows for a diverse range of disadvantaged entrepreneurs. The launch of this new financing scheme might be in response to a challenge that CEDA had faced in serving small businesses. According to a report by the World Bank (2022), CEDA also offers a microfinance product, Mabogo-Dinku, which is a short-term group-loan product for micro-enterprises. Micro-enterprises can use these funds for operational expenses, working capital or capital expenditure for equipment. A group of 5-15 members is required to qualify for the

loan where each member is willing to co-guarantee their fellow members. Each member should be a micro-entrepreneur. Members are also expected to save on a monthly basis and these savings are deposited in an Absa Motshelo account. These groups meet on a regular basis to ensure that the loans are being repaid by members. Currently, this product has around 5,000 members, though it is not clear how many MSMEs actually have accessed the funds. CEDA also launched a microfinance product for individuals operating in the informal sector in 2020. The product, Lethabile, was initially set up to support informal microenterprises during the COVID-19 pandemic. However, CEDA is looking to extend this program going forward. **CEDA microfinance lending is constrained by a lack of capacity and the heavy administrative burden** required to execute a group community-based microfinance product (World Bank, 2022). In our study, it is found out that CEDA indeed offers a wide array of loans from seven-digit loans to smaller loans starting as low as BWP 10,000 (EUR 680) that is accessible to micro enterprises or individuals.

In the sphere of **climate funds**, many development funds for green energy transition still focus on large and centralised energy projects. Needs-based and decentralised energy solutions were often assessed as lacking legal certainty and funding, hence also lacking investment (BMZ, 2017). For small actors engaged in the commercialisation of the SteamBioAfrica solid biofuel in rural areas, such investment approach is less than favourable.

4.1.2 National banks

National banks are governmental institutions that oversee a country's monetary policies and regulate the financial system. Their mandate is generally to promote the country's sustainable economic growth and financial stability. The South African Reserve Bank, Bank of Namibia, and Bank of Botswana are mainly responsible for overseeing financial policies and regulating other financial institutions that provide credits to MSMEs. Hence, national banks have a more indirect impact for loan-seeking MSMEs. However, national banks play a key role in ensuring a stable macroeconomic environment and encouraging other financial actors to lend to small businesses.

4.1.3 Commercial banks

Commercial banks are private or publicly-traded financial institutions that provide a range of banking services to individuals, businesses, and other organisations. They are traditionally the most common source of funding for people in need of money (Siyongwana, 2004). In the context of the SteamBioAfrica project, loans from commercial banks are found to be the most relevant financing schemes to consider for solid biofuel sellers or other supply chain actors.

In South Africa two banks were found to offer viable loans for MSMEs in the biomass value chains. The Standard Bank of South Africa offers small loans starting from ZAR 500 (EUR 25) for applicants who are able to fulfil the admission criteria and pay initiation and monthly service fees. The amount of interest rates are unknown until applying for a loan and only on the amount used there will be charges. Secondly, the ABSA Bank offers specific funding for MSMEs if the enterprise has been awarded a contract or purchase order by a public sector entity.

In Namibia a wide range of banks were identified. The Agribank and the Development Bank of Namibia (DBN) were identified to offer many different finance options for MSMEs such as communal farmers as well as women and youth and start-up enterprises. Agribank targets larger scale agriculture projects, but also provides loans to a group of MSMEs that apply for

loans through an intermediary. DBN also offers small loans for actors in the retail sector. In both cases the interest rates depend on various factors, such as the loan size and creditworthiness. Both banks were deeper investigated by the SteamBioAfrica project of which the results are outlined in Section 4.1.3.2. In addition, the Bank Windhoek and First National Bank Namibia (FNB) also offer MSME financing to entrepreneurs who are especially active in the agriculture sector.

In Botswana, the Stanbic Bank Botswana (SBB), National Development Bank (NDB) and First National Bank (FNB) were identified to offer financing to MSMEs. Both SBB and NDB support a diverse range of business projects and charge interest rates. The two banks offer customised interest rates. However, the interest rates charged by NDB are known to range between 2% – 16% for a business loan. FNB also offers customised interest rates depending on the financing package.

4.1.3.1 MSMEs challenges to access commercial banks

Although commercial banks are traditionally the most common way to access loans, in South Africa 75% of MSME credit applications have seen rejection (Um et al., 2018). More recently, during the COVID-19 pandemic, the country has set up a 200 billion Rand loan-guarantee scheme in partnership with commercial banks, from which until the end of 2020 only less than 1% of MSMEs has benefited (Cunha et al., 2020). This showcases a systematic and long-standing financing challenge MSMEs face in South Africa.

On the supply side, it was found out that banks had followed cumbersome manual processes requiring hard copy documents and in-branch applications, and generally lacked efforts to digitalisation. On the demand side, borrowers seemed to be reluctant to take on new debts to further leverage their businesses during the pandemic (Cunha et al., 2020). Not only during times of crises and within South Africa such challenges to a well-functioning finance system were identified.

Furthermore, for MSMEs it is difficult to access financing as they must have a good credit history and some form of collateral, for instance in the form of fixed property as the Agribank of Namibia requires. Startups and informal enterprises which often do not possess credit history or collateral are hence seen as ‘high-risk clientele’ by commercial banks. In the AFI report (2020), specific constraints facing commercial banks when it comes to lending to MSMEs were identified in an African context (Ssettimba et al., 2020). Among others, a shortage of bankable projects, a lack of effective collateral, a lack of managerial capacity, informality and a high default rate among MSMEs were mentioned as main obstacles to MSME lending (Figure 5).

Figure 5: EIB report Banking in Africa – financing transformation amid uncertainty.

Further reasons that impede MSMEs to access financing at banks were small cash flows, high risk premiums, under-developed bank-borrower relationship, as well as the fear of high interest rates and complex application processes (Otchere et al., 2017). The fact that banks require an existing relationship through lending or transactional banking with MSMEs (Cunha et al., 2020) showcases both the uncertainty of lenders towards actors in the MSME sector and the difficulty for MSME newcomers to establish a foothold.

4.1.4 SBA and the Development Bank of Namibia and Agribank

In March 2023 the SteamBioAfrica project team attempted to engage with the Development Bank of Namibia and the Agribank of Namibia to identify financing options for MSMEs operating in the downstream of biomass value chains. The SBA team introduced the project and products, i.e. the superheated steam technology and solid biofuel, to the banks. These direct engagements confirmed a common risk aversion shared by banks and financial institutions in general toward MSME financing due to a high rate of default cases among micro- and small-sized businesses. However, the two banks acknowledged the importance of supporting MSMEs for local economic development.

When asked about what the Namibian MSMEs can do to obtain financing, at least **two potential avenues** came to light. DBN’s approach to MSME financing is through **group or third-party guarantees**. When MSMEs organise themselves into a group, where some of its members could lend their creditworthiness to their group and play a role as intermediaries between banks and MSMEs, it is possible for the group to apply for credit to the bank. If the “intermediary” has an established track record, DBN will be willing to lend to the group. Once agreed and approved, DBN will channel the funds via the intermediary enterprise – acting as the MSME group leader – which will, in turn, distribute the funds to its group members. The intermediary enterprise is then responsible to organise its members to ensure a timely repayment of loans. With this arrangement, the bank’s transaction costs can be lowered as it deals only with one enterprise instead of many – which may not be able to acquire loans individually due to their small size – and the arrangement can reduce the risk of defaults among MSMEs.

Slightly different from DBN, the Agribank of Namibia – having the mandate to support agricultural enterprises in Namibia – is less risk averse when it comes to MSME lending. However, Agribank also seeks to lend to MSMEs having a track record with the bank or

having a financial record. The Agribank provides training programmes to agricultural MSMEs to enhance MSMEs' organisational and financial capacity, thus making them reliable partners to the bank.

4.1.5 Microfinance

Microfinancing refers to the provision of financial services, such as small loans (micro-loans), savings accounts, insurance, and other financial products, to individuals and small businesses that lack access to traditional banking services (Agbloyor et al., 2021). In Africa, microfinance has existed for a long time through susu (savings schemes) and Rotating Savings and Credit Associations (ROSCAs) where members save money for a given period and a member of the group receives a loan based on the savings of the group. One of the biggest contributions of microfinance to Africa's development agenda is its contribution to promoting financial inclusion. This is particularly important given the low levels of financial inclusion in Africa (Agbloyor et al., 2021).

Within the aforementioned government programmes, as well as development banks (such as Development Bank of Namibia), microfinancing service exists.

Initially microfinancing was created to help people get out of poverty in developing countries, which now can help bridge MSMEs with the needed financing. The Micro Agricultural Financial Institutions (MAFISA) in **South Africa** have a focus on micro-credit provision. It offers financing for enterprises and smallholders in the agriculture, forestry and fishery sector. To ensure small businesses are being targeted, applicants cannot have high turnover and financing is provided in the form of materials (e.g., seeds, technology). Another example is the Kongalend Microfinance in **Namibia**. It focuses on supporting micro- and small-size enterprises through, for example, its SMME Power Loan, as well as SMEs in the sectors such as sustainable agriculture, green energy supply, and biomass harvesting and processing through its Green Impact Finance. Microloans can be accessed short term (working capital finance) or long term (asset backed finance). **In Botswana**, the Prolude Capital is a new microfinance institution which is still forging its way into the local financing landscape, offering microfinance to Botswanan MSMEs.

4.2 Digital finance, non-bank financial institutions (NBFIs) and fintech

In the last 10 years, partially digitised banking has risen extremely fast. Many commercial banks, including those presented above, now offer online banking, automated machines that accept payment via debit cards or even the possibility to turn a smartphone into a card machine (ABSA Bank South Africa). This is increasingly helpful for MSME actors that want to avoid bureaucracy and do not have the capacity to visit banks in person. For banks themselves, digital services reduce the cost of intermediating with smaller clients and provide deposit collection at a lower cost, as well as relieving some pressure on branch networks to fulfil their client servicing mandate (Ssettimba et al., 2020). Besides this trend towards more digitised banking options in existing commercial banking, almost fully digitalised finance solutions such as non-bank financial intermediaries (NBFI) and fintech companies are in an African context on the rise.

4.2.1 Non-bank financial intermediaries

Non-bank financial intermediaries (NBFIs) encompass numerous firms with distinct business models that provide various financial services (Ehrentraud et al., 2024). This includes NBFIs retail lenders, such as finance companies, mortgage companies, fintechs and big techs that lend to households and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). A focus area in the deployment of technology is to lower the cost of and reduce the risks associated with providing loans to MSMEs (Ssettimba et al., 2020).

The **digitisation** of key MSME client journeys to increase customer satisfaction offers significant potential. In South Africa, most non-bank financial institutions (NBFIs) have already digitised their application-to-loan-disbursal process, enabling them to provide financing to MSMEs efficiently and conveniently. They require little to no paperwork and have quicker turnaround times than banks, and thus offer a better customer experience (Cunha et al., 2020). According to Ssettimba et al., 2020 the trend towards digitisation in financial services takes many forms and is ever-evolving as evident below:

- The digitisation of delivery and payment channels (mobile and Internet banking, digital payments) is well established.
- The use of mobile money (e-money), where Africa has been the leader for more than a decade.
- The increased digitisation of services in banks and other financial service providers / FSPs (e.g. automated processes and digital client support).
- The incorporation of fintech in the products and services offered by FSPs.
- Fintech offering services directly, where regulations would allow it.

Digital credit refers to loans that are delivered and repaid digitally, typically over a mobile phone (Kaffenberger and Totolo, 2018). The AFI report (Ssettimba et al., 2020) further characterises digital loans as follows:

- Instant. Digital lenders use digital data, such as airtime top-ups, mobile phone call records, and app-based data (on smartphones), on potential borrowers to make near-instant credit decisions. Disbursement also happens quickly because loans are delivered digitally.
- Automated. From registration to application, disbursement, and repayment, lender decisions and actions are automated, based on pre-set parameters.
- Remote. Loan applications, disbursements, and repayments are managed and conducted remotely, generally eliminating human interaction from the loan process.

Furthermore, NBFIs have developed their ability to repackage their lending products as funding solutions. Instead of restricting what borrowed funds can be used for, NBFIs allow MSMEs to determine how to use the funds and price the risk accordingly. Additionally, the majority of NBFIs offer **unsecured products**, thereby making it easier for businesses in the missing middle to qualify (Cunha et al., 2020).

NBFIs are innovating their business models in other ways too. For example, an NBFI providing financing to spaza-shop owners equipped customers with a till device and takes a portion of each transaction. This collection model directly links to sales and the customer's cash flow and the NBFI can gather valuable data on its customers, which helps inform its risk assessments (Cunha et al., 2020). Generally, NBFIs can be a showcase for banks on how to

assess customers' risk profiles through alternative data sources. Advanced analytics such as digital credit assessment could be based on prior transactions or even social media

4.2.2 Fintechs

Fintechs are companies that rely primarily on technology and cloud services—and less so on physical locations—to provide financial services to customers (McKinsey & Company, 2024)

Digitisation is expected to provide an important avenue for African economies to advance across different sectors. In agriculture, which employs over 65% of the population across the region, there is an increasing transition from in-person service provision to new digital platforms offering services even in the most remote locations. Some advantages of offering digital financial service to small businesses are illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Benefits of MSME fintech lending (Source: Dutt et al., 2018 from WEF, 2015)

South Africa has a vibrant fintech sector. Accounting for 40% of all fintech revenue in Africa, the country has a relatively mature fintech market. The largest and most mature subsector is payments, with 30% of companies in South Africa operating in this space, most of them for more than five years (Fahad, 2023). For example, two fintech companies were studied in this report, i.e. Lula and Nomanini. Lula offers various digital financial services to businesses, such as business funding (Lulalend Revolving Capital Facility, Capital Advance), business banking (for businesses to manage their cash flow), and Trade capital (“Buy now, pay later”

facility). Nomanini, dedicated to payment, is a pioneering fintech platform that tries to connect global distributors and service providers to local merchants in informal markets across the continent. Nomanini’s Trader Solutions provides informal traders with access to credit advances in real-time, as well as access to other financial services such as savings and insurance tailored to the needs of informal retail MSMEs.

In Namibia, the fintech sector is still in development. The Namibia Financial Institutions Supervisory Authority (NAMFISA), for example, was organising the Fintech Square Program in May 2024 to promote fintech in the country. **In Botswana**, new fintech startups start to surface (Tracxn, 2024). It remains to be seen if all the 10 fintech startups will be able to remain viable in the local financial market.

4.2.2.1 Fintech in Africa’s financial landscape

The IFAD 2023 report (Litvinova et al., 2023) explores the universe of agritech and fintech providers (Figure 7) that influence access to finance for small-scale farmers and agricultural MSMEs in East and Southern Africa, exploring their potential to become commercially viable and achieve scale.

Fintech		
Business model	Company	Geography
Credit Scoring	FarmDrive	Kenya
	Oko Finance	Uganda
Insurance	Acre Africa	Broader ESA
	SproutInsure	Kenya
	Offgrid Finance	Kenya
Lending	Agri-Wallet	Kenya
	Capture Solutions	Kenya
	Juhudi Kilimo	Kenya
	FACTS Africa	Broader ESA
	ZuriCap Limited	Kenya
	Emata	Uganda
	Payments	Nomanini

Figure 7: Examples of African fintech companies (Litvinova et al., 2023, p. 37)

Despite its potentials, IFAD also found that so far the **agriculture-related fintech has the lowest number of transactions and funding in the region**, with challenges in proving its value proposition; lending and insurance are the most common business models in the segment (Figure 8).

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Figure 8: Fintech investment activities (IFAD report, 2023)

In its 2022 report, the International Finance Corporation (IFC) also showed how agricultural technology (AgTech) companies hold great potential to increase **financial service provision** to smallholder farmers and agri-SMEs in Africa. The report identified several **business models** that provide varying competencies to enable financial services directly and indirectly.

On the business to consumer (B2C) side, many business models were operating in the space, but only a few commercial players (e.g., AFEX, Apollo Agriculture) have proven to be viable. Challenges including weak infrastructure and reliance on field agents create **barriers** for these AgTechs to scale.

Furthermore, a lack of debt funding has forced AgTechs to provide loans to clients using costly equity which leads to high costs passed down to the end user. Partnerships between commercial banks and AgTechs hold potential to reduce costs and capitalise on AgTechs' ability to reach and de-risk rural consumers, however partnership models are not yet widespread in the region (IFC, 2022).

On the B2B side, the number of providers that directly enable financial services is still very few. A few players (e.g., SatSure, CropIn) have managed to tailor their services for financial service providers. However, many others are only just beginning to think through how their data can enable agricultural financing (IFC, 2022).

4.3 *Alternative financing schemes*

4.3.1 *Blended finance*

Blended finance is a funding instrument that combines capital from the public (government) or philanthropic sources (e.g., international funds) with private investments (e.g., banks) to finance projects contributing to sustainable development goals (Rukero & Blumenthal, 2023). Due to public investment, private institutions or individual investors have a higher incentive to allocate resources towards projects they would otherwise deem as too risky or unprofitable. Essentially, blended finance seeks to “de-risk” potential investments through public money in such a way that private sector actors will feel comfortable investing alongside or on top (Runde et al., 2021).

In South Africa, the ECRDA – SEFA Rural Blended Finance scheme and AGRO Energy Fund are particularly relevant to MSMEs operating in the biomass value chains. The first ECRDA–SEFA scheme focuses on general rural development and fosters access to finance among MSMEs such as informal traders, primary producers or manufacturers in the agricultural sector. The Small Enterprise Finance Agency (SEFA) is, in fact, the South African government’s main finance arm dedicated to small businesses and cooperatives (Um et al., 2018), that provides **microfinance services**. In collaboration with SEFA, the Eastern Cape Rural Development Agency (ECRDA) provides a package of loans and grants, which primarily aims to contribute to entrepreneurs’ working capital, movable assets, and technical skill enhancement.

The AGRO Energy Fund targets the middle- to large-scale agricultural projects linked to energy intensive farming (e.g., irrigation, intensive agricultural production systems and on-farm cold chain related activities). Applicants must already have a well-established business and fulfil highly formal criteria. Funding can be received through a purchase of capital equipment and infrastructure for alternative energy sources directly linked to energy-intensive farming operations. This financing scheme can be relevant for future investment in the superheated steam (SHS) technology that the SteamBioAfrica project has developed.

In Namibia, the Green Impact Facility (GIF) receives funding from the Environmental Investment Fund (EIF) and seeks to bring together stakeholders from development finance institutions to philanthropic organisations to provide financing to SMEs. GIF innovates through providing blended finance to SMEs. In operation since March 2023, GIF has allocated its NAD 72 million (EUR 3,6 million) capital, collaborating with local fund managers such as the Kongalend Financial Service and Bellatrix SME Finance. With 95 approved loans, GIF seeks to promote financial inclusion, create new jobs and finance projects in renewable energy and sustainable agriculture (EIF, online). The **Namibia Biomass Industry Group (N-Big)**, a **SteamBioAfrica partner**, has **successfully engaged with and signed an MoU with the Kongalend Financial Service** to provide financing to MSMEs that are members of N-Big’s network. This access to SME finance will encourage the MSMEs to take part in the SBA solid biofuel value chains.

In Botswana, direct blended finance has not been identified. However, it can be expected that innovative funds and facilities supporting blended finance will rise in the future, especially for decentralised renewables in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) (Corfee-Morlot et al., 2019).

The growth of blended finance, such as the aforementioned ECRDA–SEFA scheme, could lead to the emergence of similar financing schemes in the Southern African region, which is

inclusive to the informal sector. To date, blended finance has mobilised approximately \$152 billion in private capital in Sub-Saharan Africa (Runde et al., 2021). Despite this achievement, the funding currently available through blended finance remains only a fraction of what is needed to help countries meet their SDGs by 2030 (Corfee-Morlot et al., 2019).

4.3.2 Angel investment

Angel investment refers to capital provided by affluent individuals, known as angel investors, to early-stage startups or small businesses in exchange for ownership equity or convertible debt. These investments are typically used to support the company's growth during its initial phases when access to other forms of financing, such as bank loans or venture capital, might be limited. **In Namibia**, the Business Angel Network (NABAN) is present and aims to champion angel investment into startups and early-stage companies.

In South Africa, the South African Angel Investment Network (SAAIN) offers a paid membership platform connecting entrepreneurs with angel investors (both local and international) and helps them get funded. Jozi Angels is an angel network based in Johannesburg, South Africa. It seeks to grow the startup ecosystem and facilitate the growth of innovative startups.

4.3.3 Crowdfunding

Crowdfunding is a method of raising capital through the collective effort of friends, family, customers, and individual investors. This approach taps into the collective efforts of a large pool of individuals – primarily online via social media and crowdfunding platforms. Although it has grown rapidly since the mid of the 2000s, it still represents only a minor share of business financing. The World Bank Group report (2019) assessed equity crowdfunding, where investors receive a stake in an enterprise with significant potential. The ability to effectively reach out to one's social network (essentially a kind of informal crowdfunding) is even more important due to the lack of formal credit options. In most developing economies, less than 10% of consumers report borrowing from formal financial institutions (World Bank Group, 2019).

In South Africa, there are many crowdfunding platforms, such as Jumpstarter, Backabuddy, Thundafund, and Uprise.Africa. Crowdfunding is legal in South Africa, but there are no specific laws regulating crowdfunding in the country. Some aspects are, however, regulated locally through the Companies Act of 2008 and the Banks Act of 1990 (Writer, 2020). **In Namibia and Botswana**, no local crowdfunding platforms could be identified. However, there are several US America-based crowdfunding platforms that could be identified, for example Kickstarter and Indiegogo (Faster Capital, online).

4.3.4 Further alternative financing schemes

In the international finance arena, discussions on broadening the range of financing schemes for MSMEs are ongoing. Table 6 provides a quick overview of MSME alternative financing schemes that have been discussed in international forums.

Financing scheme	Description
Asset-based finance	It is a widespread form of finance for SMEs, used to monetise the value of specific assets and access working capital under more flexible terms than they could from conventional lending channels. As firms obtain funding based on the value of specific assets, including accounts receivables, inventory, machinery, equipment and real estate, rather than on their own credit standing, asset-based finance can serve the financing needs of start-up and small firms that have difficulties in accessing traditional lending. In the forms of factoring and leasing, asset-based finance is widely used in many countries.
Factoring	It is defined as a type of supplier financing, in which enterprises (sellers) sell their creditworthy accounts receivable at a discount (generally equal to interest plus service fees) and receive immediate cash from a specialised institution, or factor. In other words, the factor buys the right to collect an enterprise's invoices from its customers, by paying the firm the face value of these invoices, less a discount.
Leasing	It is a three-party arrangement, where one party, the lessor, buys an asset from the supplier upon request of the lessee (e.g. the MSME) and leases this asset to the lessee for a certain period in exchange for leasing payments. The total value of leasing payments may or may not amortise the cost of the leased asset.
Debt securitisation and covered bonds	These are instruments for the refinancing of banks and their portfolio risk management. In essence, banks would package and sell a portion of their loan book to raise finance for further business activity. This market has developed significantly, although the global financial crisis slowed this development for a while. These are important instruments to foster SME lending, as the process of securitization draws in other funders that are not necessarily engaged in the MSME market.
Hybrid instruments	These combine debt and equity features into a single financing vehicle. These techniques represent an appealing form of finance for enterprises that are approaching a turning point in their life cycle. When the risks and opportunities of the business are increasing, a capital injection is needed, but these enterprises have limited or no access to debt financing or equity, e.g. young high-growth companies. Governments can use one of the mechanisms that have been deployed in a country to participate in these instruments, typically by establishing a fund or funds for a specific purpose, e.g. innovation funds.
Equity finance	It comprises all financial resources that are provided to the firms in return for an ownership interest. These include public instruments, i.e. equity shares traded in some form of a stock exchange, and private equity tools, which are relevant for the unlisted companies' market. Equity investors do not receive any security from the investee company and their return is entirely determined by the success of the entrepreneurial venture. Equity financing is especially relevant for companies that have a high risk-return profile, such as new, innovative and high growth firms. Seed and early-stage equity finance can boost firm creation and development.
Venture capital and angel investing (private equity)	These are typically targeting a small pool of high-growth potential companies, with the capacity for high returns in a short timeframe. The two forms are similar in some respects but are characterised by different motivations, stage of investment, scale and operating models. Business angels invest their own money, rather than collecting funds from a variety of investors, focus mainly on the seed and early stage, contrarily to venture capitalists' increasing focus on later stages, bring into the venture their own entrepreneurial skills and expertise, with a more hands-on role in the company than venture capitalists.

Table 6: Overview of alternative MSME financing (Adapted from: [AFI report](#), 2020)

4.4 Informal Finance

Informal financing is financing that occurs without a formal financial intermediary between savers and borrowers. Informal financing often includes but is not restricted to trade credit, interpersonal borrowing (money from friends or families), private money houses, pawnshops, community cooperatives, and so on. In Sub-Saharan Africa, on average only 9% of adults save formally with higher numbers in Namibia and South Africa (Demirguc-Kunt et al., 2017). New developments in fintech such as people to people (P2P) and crowdfunding seem to draw on the intermediation advantages of bank financing and the information advantage of financing within social and business networks (Allen et al, 2019).

In the context of this report, little could be found about informal financing schemes that are publicly accessible and can be found on the Internet. In Botswana, Namibia and South Africa, a few financing possibilities were offered on social media platforms, particularly Facebook. The web pages offering these loans were often characterised with catchy and colourful pictures, and called for direct action due to a limited time that the loan was available. Ensuring credibility of these financing sources was difficult since the informal financial providers generally do not have a website. Instead, they provide personal contact details. The only way to contact the money-lenders was through an indicated phone number or direct messages via Facebook.

According to a study on informal money-lenders in South Africa (Siyongwana, 2004), informal money-lending is a vital business on its own and used largely by the poorest of the nation. The loans offered are mostly short term, based on trust, and impose incredibly high interest rates on users. The people using such loans are at the risk of entering a debt-trap and becoming totally dependent on informal loans to survive. The lack of access to formal finance brings certain entrepreneurs in need in the situation to depend on informal financing, hence making this scheme a crucial financing method for MSMEs.

5 SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Tackling climate change in Africa presents a US\$3 trillion economic investment opportunity in the continent by 2030. It is vital for the private sector in the region to adapt to, as well as mitigate, the climate change impact. Micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) make up a significant part of Africa's private sector. Hence, it is critical to incentivise MSMEs to operate in a sustainable way in order to achieve a sustainable green growth, which improves their resilience towards climate change.

Southern African countries are currently facing challenges of **bush encroachment**, where the overgrowths compete with farmlands and livestock for water and land. The encroachment is caused by a combination of factors, including climate change.

The EU-funded Horizon2020 SteamBioAfrica (SBA) project seeks to turn this problem into an opportunity. It demonstrates the potential of superheated steam (SHS) technology to turn the unwanted and otherwise-wasted biomass into a new, clean burning solid biofuel, and offers value to the local market as well as possibility for farmers and landowners to finance a sustainable land management. Without creating financial value out of the encroaching bush, it is deemed impossible to control the bush encroachment as the land management proves to be very costly without any immediate value to be seen.

The overarching objective of this Work Package 10 (WP10) is to facilitate a wide-scale commercialisation of the clean-burning solid biofuel, which is generated by the SHS plant, that the project has installed and demonstrated at the Cheetah Conservation Fund (CCF) in Otjiwarongo, Namibia. As part of WP10, the project seeks to identify existing as well as innovative financing schemes that may cater to the needs of MSMEs operating in the biomass value chains in Botswana, Namibia and South Africa. This Deliverable 10.5 report explores the topic of innovative MSME financing available in the Southern African region.

In Sub-Saharan Africa, **solid biofuels** contribute to over 60% of the total potential of bioenergy. This **huge potential** offers not only climate benefits, but also local economic and socio-economic benefits. However, MSMEs often face challenges in accessing finance to start, maintain and sustain their business growth. It is, therefore, **important to support the biomass MSMEs** in the Southern African region to access finance. The SBA project seeks to facilitate the takeup of the new clean-burning solid biofuel by local MSMEs, thereby creating a local demand for the biofuel and, in turn, a need for investments in the innovative SHS technology to counter the bush encroachment problem specific to the region.

This report identifies **four types of financing sources** relevant to the biomass sector, i.e., traditional financing, digital financing, innovative financing, and informal financing. Each type has a prospect of providing access to MSME finance particularly to those operating in the biomass value chains in the three countries of Botswana, Namibia and South Africa.

Furthermore, this report also finds out that:

- MSME financing schemes are mostly offered by **government-initiated funds** and **commercial banks, particularly development banks**. These organisations can play a big role in the financing landscape of biomass MSMEs. This is partly due to the fact that the SBA solid biofuel is new to the market – hence it can be considered as a ‘risky’ business – and it is a simple product used for cooking and heating of homes.
- **Public finance** needs to be raised but will also be limited in the face of the scale of investments required. **Private finance** will need to drive the change. Limited public finance needs to be efficient and to leverage private investment and finance. **Innovative green finance** platforms, policies and instruments in the **blended finance** arena are necessary but, on their own, will not be sufficient; they need to be coupled with national policies establishing enabling conditions for private investment and MSME capacity building on financial and business planning.
- **Innovative and digital financing** can play a bigger role in enhancing MSME access to finance as the technology is spreading in the region. A lack of debt funding forces agricultural fintech companies (agtechs) to provide loans to clients using costly equity which lead to high costs passed down to the end user. **Facilitating partnerships** between commercial banks and agtechs holds potential to reduce costs and capitalise on agtechs’ ability to reach and de-risk rural consumers.
- **The number of financial technology providers** that directly enable financial services is still very few. A few players manage to tailor their services for financial service providers. However, many others are only just beginning to think how their data can enable agricultural financing. Governments can play a proactive role to encourage a vibrant local digital finance sector.
- Potential contribution of **digital financial services** to improve efficiencies (thereby reducing cost) and making access to such services far more widespread (thereby

increasing reach) requires on-going support from all stakeholders, including regulatory authorities.

- The use of alternative data to develop new credit products and the potential of digital financial services is key in providing banking services to MSMEs and digitising specific agricultural value chains (e.g. solid biofuel) in the process.
- Key players in innovative and digital financing still favour digital and fintech startups more than small agri-forestry enterprises. **Biomass MSMEs with clear business plans** and **innovative business models** can still benefit from other alternative financing such as **crowdfunding**, or a combination of other financing schemes (government-initiated funds, MSME loans by commercial banks, microfinance).
- **Consistent historical track record** with banks and financial institutions over the years is particularly important for MSMEs as they seek to access financing and may not have collaterals. Small retailers and sellers that have worked with the SBA project may not need a huge credit from banks, that necessitate a sizable collateral. A fintech company, e.g. Nomanini in South Africa, showcases how fintech can strategically bridge MSMEs in the retail sector with the financing they need by helping MSMEs build historical track records and, with that, their creditworthiness towards other financial institutions.
- **Women-owned enterprises** often face a disproportionate challenge in accessing finance as banks consider women as ‘riskier clientele’. At the same time, these enterprises tend to employ more women. Thus, supporting women-owned businesses by enhancing their access to finance will have a greater influence on gender equity and economic development across the continent.
- **Through a participatory approach**, governments can formulate differentiated financial inclusion policies for women-owned MSMEs, but also for MSMEs in general. Such policies can also target financial literacy among MSMEs through targeted capacity building programmes.

Finally, it is worth mentioning that the SBA solid biofuel has a huge potential for industrial use (as fuels for boilers in various industrial facilities such as cement factories, breweries and foundry). However, this report puts more focus on the access to finance for MSMEs operating in the downstream of the biomass value chains (distribution, retail and consumption).

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8 APPENDIX: IDENTIFIED MSME FINANCING SCHEMES FOR BIOMASS SECTOR IN BOTSWANA, NAMIBIA AND SOUTH AFRICA

1 APPENDIX 1 IDENTIFIED MSME FINANCING SCHEMES FOR BIOMASS SECTOR IN BOTSWANA, NAMIBIA AND SOUTH AFRICA

Country	Financial institution	Description	Financing type	Financing package	Sector	Type of enterprise	Amount	Requirements	Interest rest pa (%)	Duration (year)
BOT	National Development Bank (NDB)	State-owned bank	Loan	SME Loans; Retail, Commerce and Industry	Agriculture; property; retail, commerce & industry, etc.	Legally registered enterprises, etc.	Up to BWP 4 million (EUR 275,000) for SME Loan	Botswana citizens; Legally registered companies	depending on type of loan: 2%-16%	1 - 15
BOT	Citizen Entrepreneurial Development Agency (CEDA) – Credit Guarantee Scheme (CCGS)	Government-initiated fund	Loan	Loan finance, CEDA Credit Guarantee Scheme (CCGS)	Agribusiness, trade finance	Start-ups, enterprises, micro-scale projects	Trade finance: BWP 500 - 30 million (EUR 35 - 2 million) CCGS: BWP 10,000 - 4 million (EUR 680 - 275,000)	Citizen-owned businesses; personal guarantee over assets often required. CCGS provides a guarantee of up to 75%	Varied depending on loan size. E.g. 5% for BWP 500,000. CCGS: 1.5% pa guarantee fee	1
BOT	CEDA – Chema Chema	Government-initiated fund	Loan	Chema Chema	Diverse	Individuals, informal enterprises, MSMEs, women and youth entrepreneurs	BWP 15,000 - 50,000 (EUR 1,000 - 3,400)	Citizens, having a business idea / plan	2.4	1
BOT	First National Bank (FNB)	Commercial Bank	Loan	Various	Diverse	Diverse	Customized	Annual financial statements If not customer at FPN: Management accounts, Business plan	Customized	Max 5 years
BOT	Stanbicbank	Commercial Bank	Loan	Business term loan Business overdraft Commercial property loan Vehicle and asset finance	Diverse	Companies, Joint-ventures, and Partnerships	Varied	N/A	Customized	Customized

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BOT	Prolude Capital	Microfinance institution	Loan	Purchase Order Finance Invoice discounting Retail micro-lending	Diverse	SMEs	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

NAM	The Agribank of Namibia	State-owned bank	Loan	Various	Agriculture	Commercial Farmers, Communal Farmers, Individuals, Women and Youths	Various	Security in form of fixed property, investments, or any other form of fixed investments	Varied depending on funding scheme selected	
NAM	Development Bank of Namibia	State-owned bank	Loan	Enterprise Development Finance to help start-up or expand businesses	Manufacturing, retail wholesale outlets, construction etc.	Start-ups, established enterprises: Max. annual turnover of N\$ 10 million	Min. N\$ 150,000 / EUR 7,500	Owners' equity contribution of between 10% and 30% may be required depending on project specifics and risks	Customized	Customized
NAM	Standard Bank (SB)	Commercial bank	Loan	Overdraft facility, revolving credit plan, property finance, etc	Diverse	SMEs with annual turnover up to N\$ 10 million (EUR 500,000)	N\$ 250,000 / EUR 12,500 (business overdraft)	Business must be registered etc	Varied depending on funding scheme selected	Varied
NAM	Bank Windhoek	Commercial bank	Loan	Overdraft facility, commercial building loan, business loan, emerging small and medium enterprise financing	Diverse	Any SMEs	Depending on the applicants annual turnovers (for overdrafts)	Business must be registered etc	Varied depending on funding scheme selected	1 (overdraft facility) to 15 (business loan)
NAM	First National Bank Namibia (FNB)	Commercial bank	Loan	Overdraft facility, agricultural financing, SME business unit, credit guarantee scheme	Diverse	Start-ups, SMEs	Varied	Business must be registered, commercially viable and sustainable	Varied depending on funding scheme selected	Varied

Country	Financial institution	Description	Financing type	Financing package	Sector	Type of enterprise	Amount	Requirements	Interest rest pa (%)	Duration (year)
NAM	Kongalend	Microfinance institution	Microfinance	SMME Power Loan, Group Power Loan, People Power Loan, Green Impact Finance	Sustainability, Development	Start-ups, business expansion	N\$15,000 – 250,000 (EUR 750 – 12,500)	Businesses are required to make a cash security build-up contribution determined on the loan amount applied for, to be held as collateral	Green Impact Finance: 4%	0.5 - 4
NAM	Namibia Business Angel Network	Private Investor	Capital		Diverse					N/A
SA	Department of Trade, Industry and Competition (DTIC)	Government-initiated fund	Reimbursable grant	Agro-processing support scheme Black industrialist scheme Strategic partnership programme	Agro-processing, agriculture industry, green investments	New and existing agro-processing / beneficiation projects	Max. EUR 1,000,000	A reimbursable grant of between 20% up to a 30% cost sharing grant to a maximum of ZAR 20 million	N/A	2
SA	Department of economic development, environmental affairs and tourism in the Eastern Cape - DEDEA	Government-initiated fund	Grant and co-funding		Agro-industry value chain, Auto, Manufacturing, Oceans economy, sustainable energy, tourism, Services/Retail, Creative industry, Information & Communication Technology, Franchise	Start-ups & existing enterprises	Max. ZAR 3 million / EUR 150,000	Grants: companies, cooperatives, close corporations whose directors and/or members do not have any other operating business interests Co-funding: varied depending on turnover	N/A	N/A
SA	Eastern Cape Development Agency (ECRDA) & Small Enterprise Finance Agency (SEFA) Rural Blended Finance Scheme	Government-initiated fund	Blended financing		All rural sectors include retail, informal traders, primary producers, agro-processing, manufactures,	Rural entrepreneurs and agro processing enterprises operating in a township or the rural environment	Max. ZAR 2,5 million / EUR 125,000	The business must be 100% owned by South African nationals; Willing to participate in the DSBD / SEDA	From 5% on loan component	Up to 5

Country	Financial institution	Description	Financing type	Financing package	Sector	Type of enterprise	Amount	Requirements	Interest rest pa (%)	Duration (year)	
					forestry and livestock development			facilitated business development process; The enterprise must be operating in a township or rural environment			
SA	National Empowerment Fund (NEF)	Government-initiated fund	Loan	Alternative Energy Fund	Various	Registered companies, close corporations or cooperatives	ZAR 5 million / EUR 250,000	Proven commercial viability, compliance to laws and regulations, operational involvement by Black people, minimum percentage of ownership by Black people, business must be able to repay NEF funding, business must create a reasonable number of jobs	2% for the initial ZAR 5 million	7	
				Women Empowerment Fund	Energy solutions	Black-owned startups or businesses to install green energy solutions	ZAR 250,000 - 75 million (EUR 12,500 - 3,7 million)			N/A	
			Loan, quasi-equity and equity finance products	iMbewu Fund	Various	Businesses owned by Black women	ZAR 250,000 - 15 million (EUR 12,500 - 750,000)			N/A	
			Varied	uMnotho Fund	Various	Black entrepreneurs wishing to start new businesses or support Black-owned enterprises with expansion capital	ZAR 2 - 50 million (EUR 100,000 - 2,5 million)			N/A	
			Loan, equity and quasi-equity instruments	Rural Township & Community Development Fund	Various	Rural enterprises	N/A			N/A	5 - 10
				Strategic Projects Fund	Various	Sustainable Enterprise	N/A			N/A	N/A

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SA	AGRO Energy Fund (AEF)	Government-initiated fund	Blended finance		Energy intensive agriculture activities (e.g. irrigation, agricultural production)	Smallholder Producers Medium Scale Producers Large Scale Producers Mega commercial producers	Purchase of capital equipment and infrastructure for alternative energy sources directly linked to energy-intensive farming operations	For implementing an energy efficiency project or to implement a project that partially offsets electricity from the grid through self-use renewable energy; operating an agricultural business at the primary or secondary level	Varied depending on the financing scheme selected	Depending on funding schemes
SA	Micro Agricultural Financial Institutions of South Africa (MAFISA) Scheme	Government-initiated fund	Micro-credit	Development Fund	Agriculture, forestry, fishery	Smallholder farmers and agribusinesses (Gross non-farm income should not be more than ZAR 20,000 / EUR 1,000 per month)	Max. ZAR 500,000 / EUR 25,000	Citizens, from historically disadvantaged groups, able to demonstrate business viability, collaterals required for loans above ZAR 25,000 (EUR 1,200), loans available to individuals and groups	8	Repayment tied to income cycle of the enterprise
SA	Technology Innovation Agency (TIA)	Government-initiated fund for micro-enterprises	Grant, loan, innovation seed fund	Seed fund; Technology fund; Pre-commercialisation support fund	Natural resources, energy, health, agriculture	SMEs at early / risky stage	Varied	Depending on funding schemes	Varied depending on funding scheme selected	Depending on funding schemes

Country	Financial institution	Description	Financing type	Financing package	Sector	Type of enterprise	Amount	Requirements	Interest rest pa (%)	Duration (year)
SA	Standard Bank	Commercial Bank	Loan	Business overdraft Agriculture production loan Vehicle and asset finance	Various		Min. EUR 25	A Standard Bank Business Current Account to qualify for a Business Overdraft Overdraft is payable on demand and reviewed every year Initiation and monthly service fee	Customised	Customised
SA	ABSA	Commercial Bank	Grant and Loan		Various	The business should be a small to medium-sized enterprise (SME) as defined by the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) - includes start-ups and existing businesses.	EUR 2,500 to 150,000	For Fund: Business need to be awarded a contract or purchase by a public sector entity	Customised	Max. 5 years
SA	Merchant Capital	Financial institution	Loan		Various	Established: Min ZAR 50,000 or EUR 2,500 in card sales p/m	100% of business's average monthly credit	Min. ZAR 50,000 monthly turnover, owning the business for at least 12 months	Customised	Customised
SA	Lula	Fintech company	Loan, savings, trade capital		Various	Minimum of annual turnover of ZAR 500,000 / EUR 25,000	Min. ZAR 10,000 / EUR 500; Max. ZAR 5 million / EUR 250,000	A successful trading history of at least one year and annual turnover of minimum ZAR 500,000	0,3	Up to 1
SA	Retail Capital	Fintech company	Loan		Various	Minimum business ownership of 6 months; turnover min. ZAR 50,000 (EUR 2,500) per month	Customised	Proof of ownership of the business for at least 6 months; Demonstrated monthly turnover of ZAR 50,000 (EUR	Customised	Customised

Country	Financial institution	Description	Financing type	Financing package	Sector	Type of enterprise	Amount	Requirements	Interest rest pa (%)	Duration (year)
								2,500) or higher for 3 months or more		
SA	Nomanini	Fintech company	Loan		Fast moving consumer goods (FMCG)	Informal retailers, kiosk owners, MSMEs	Varied		N/A	N/A

Note: Botswana (BOT), Namibia (NAM), South Africa (SA)

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